

Race and Hispanic Origin Disagreement between the 2020 Census and Administrative Records and Potential Corrections

Dirk Bullock¹, Scott Konicki²
U.S. Census Bureau

Abstract

The 2020 Census and other data sources such as administrative records often disagree on the race and Hispanic origin of a person. If we assume that the values reported in the 2020 Census are more accurate, then we find that administrative records have a high rate of misclassification. Moreover, we find different definitions for race and Hispanic origin between data sources, which complicate comparisons. In this paper, we analyze the race and Hispanic origin classifications of people on the 2020 Census, the 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey, and the 2020 Demographic Frame of administrative records. We discuss methods for correcting misclassification of the race and Hispanic origin values on the Demographic Frame of administrative records. These include corrections to characteristics for people on the Demographic Frame of administrative records that match or do not match to the 2020 Census. Finally, we discuss the impact misclassification has on dual-system estimates of population.

Key Words: bias, dual-system estimation, matching, misclassification, multiple-race identification, post-enumeration survey, small-area estimation, variance.

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1. Introduction

Accurate Census Bureau estimates of the population by race and Hispanic origin are essential to understanding measures of inequality for these groups.³ This paper investigates differences in the race and Hispanic origin values for people in the 2020 Decennial Census, the 2020 Census Post-Enumeration Survey (PES), and a newly developed Demographic Frame of administrative records (DEMO). For reference, the Demographic Frame is a person-level frame of administrative records (Bureau of the Census, 2023). We use the disagreement of race and ethnicity between data sources as a measurement of differences in race and ethnicity reporting.⁴ We discuss the impact of disagreements in race and Hispanic origin reporting on dual-system estimates of population using the DEMO and the decennial census. We discuss alternative working methods to reduce this impact.

The Census Bureau decennial census and American Community Survey produce estimates of population by race and Hispanic origin for small geographies such as the census tract. In ongoing research, the Census Bureau aims to assess the accuracy of the decennial census and the DEMO.

¹ Email: dirk.m.bullock@census.gov

² Email: scott.m.konicki@census.gov

³ In the 2020 Census, 'Hispanic origin' and 'race' are two separate characteristics. Hispanics may be any race because 'Hispanic' is an ethnicity and not a race. However, in year 2024, the Office of Management and Budget revised Statistical Policy Directive No. 15 to combine race and ethnicity into one characteristic.

⁴ Disagreement means values are not the same. It does not assume a value is right or wrong.

This research is called the Continuous Count Study (Bureau of the Census, 2024). To perform this assessment, the Census Bureau will produce ongoing population estimates with updated counts for race and Hispanic origin. The current goal is to produce estimates at the time of the 2020 Census and a year after the 2020 Census.

We want to produce these annual population estimates at the tract level. However, there are some difficulties. For example, we want to use the population estimates from the current population estimates program as controls. Unfortunately, the current population estimates program only produces estimates at the county level, not the tract level. Moreover, we want to use updated Demographic Frames to estimate the change in race distribution. However, DEMO has a lot of race misclassification.⁵

For the Continuous Count Project, we estimate the population with a dual-system estimator. The dual-system estimator requires the match rate between 2020 Census Edited File (CEF)⁶ and DEMO person records. We match person records using a unique person identifier called the Protected Identification Key (PIK).

2. Background

The 2020 Census was subject to coverage errors. Some examples of coverage errors are not recording people or recording people more than once. The Census Bureau has relied on two principal methods to evaluate the coverage of the decennial census: the PES and Demographic Analysis (DA).

However, the PES and DA are limited in coverage measurement for race and Hispanic origin. The DA is limited to the broad race categories of Black and Non-Black and covers only certain age groups for Hispanic origin (Jensen et al., 2020). On the other hand, the PES produces population estimates for five race categories identified by Office of Management and Budget (OMB). These races are: White, Black or African American, American Indian or Alaska Native, Asian, and Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander.⁷ The PES also produces population estimates for Some Other Race and Hispanics. Albeit, the PES is a sample survey and lacks enough sample to produce quality estimates at low levels of geography. Hence, the PES only measures coverage error for the six race categories and Hispanics at the national level. More information about PES race results may be found in the PES reports (Heim et al., 2022).

Access to a person-level frame of administrative records may allow the Census Bureau to improve its operations, estimates, and evaluations at lower-levels of geography.⁸ The DEMO is such a person-level frame of administrative records. Every person record has a PIK and data fields for geography and demographic characteristics (Bureau of the Census, 2022).

The Census Bureau has ongoing research and operations for record linkage to administrative data. For instance, the Person Identification Validation System (PVS) attempts to assign a PIK to person records from survey and administrative data. This facilitates record linkage among disparate Census Bureau data sets as well as administrative data sources (Bureau of the Census, 2021).

The DEMO has broad coverage across the United States of America. The majority of CEF records match to DEMO. Furthermore, most of the CEF records that do not match to the DEMO have no assigned PIK. Often the records that could not be assigned a PIK lacked important identifying information such as a valid name or date of birth.

⁵ Conceptually, misclassification is about a false classification value. There is a true value, and a given source may classify the value incorrectly.

⁶ The Census Edited File contains person records from the census. The file contains edited and imputed data.

⁷ People may select multiple races on the 2020 Census and PES. In essence, race categories are overlapping and not mutually exclusive.

⁸ An administrative record is existing information about a person collected by the government such as social security, IRS, or U.S. postal service.

Our initial task was to produce low-level geographic, dual-system population estimates using the CEF and DEMO as the dual frames. Part of this effort involves matching the two sources to identify people who are present in both sources. However, we found many intriguing discrepancies between the CEF and DEMO. The discrepancy that is the focus of this paper is race and Hispanic origin disagreement between the CEF and DEMO.

The census is a ‘snapshot’ of how people identify themselves. Most of the respondents are enumerated through self-response or follow-up with a household member. These respondents identify their race and Hispanic origin as well as these values for other household members. Hence, we have confidence in the race and Hispanic origin responses.

Albeit, the census is prone to data collection errors such as from proxy responses and imputation errors. Proxies are respondents from outside the household, such as a neighbor or landlord. They may provide responses that would not agree with a household respondent. On the other hand, a respondent may provide some identifying information such as a name and date of birth. This may allow us to link that record with a PIK. However, these records may have missing race or Hispanic origin data. Imputation of these values is required to produce complete census counts. However, imputations may be errors.

The Demographic Frame is a person-level frame of administrative records from various administrative data sources. Some of these administrative data sources include the Internal Revenue Service (IRS) and Social Security Administration (SSA). Each DEMO record is identified with a PIK and an address identifier.

DEMO records get their race and Hispanic origin from a file called the Census Best Race file (Noon, 2024). The Census assigns Best Race from many sources including: administrative, census, survey, third-party sources, and modeling. This assignment method likely results in disagreement between the DEMO and Census. For instance, the Demographic Frame race and Hispanic origin may not reflect the most current self-identification for people.

3. Research Questions

1. What are the magnitudes and patterns of race or Hispanic origin disagreement between the matching records on the CEF and the PES?
 - a. We believe there will be less race and Hispanic origin disagreement compared to the disagreement between the CEF and DEMO. The PES was an in-person survey that asked the same race and Hispanic origin questions as the decennial census. Also, the PES occurred only a few months after the 2020 Census data collection.
2. What are the magnitudes and patterns of race or Hispanic origin disagreement between the matching records on the CEF and DEMO?
 - a. We believe that the administrative records may capture demographic characteristics differently than the census. The individual administrative record’s sources may use different categories or approaches in recording race and Hispanic origin. Further, some people in the DEMO have their race and Hispanic origin values assigned from previous census or survey responses. However, a person’s racial or ethnic self-identification can change over time. Thus, these values may not match someone’s current self-identification.
3. What are potential methods to reduce the impact of race or Hispanic origin misclassification on dual-system estimates of race or Hispanic origin populations?
 - a. We seek methods for the CEF-DEMO dual-system estimates.

4. Data and Research Methods

The following is a list of the relevant data:

- The 2020 Census Edited File
- The Demographic Frame of administrative records, dated to Census Day (April 1, 2020)
- The 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey Person Files

We produced two 8 x 8 confusion matrices to describe race and Hispanic origin disagreement between the CEF and the PES or the CEF and the DEMO. For the CEF and the PES, we only included person records for which both race and Hispanic origin were reported with no editing. For the DEMO, we only included data with non-missing race and Hispanic origin.⁹

For the CEF-DEMO dual-system estimates, we are developing and testing methods where less reliable sources borrow information from more reliable sources. Our goal is to reduce the impact from the race and Hispanic origin misclassification. We will compare these methods against each other and to baselines (methods that do not borrow information).

In essence, we assume that the CEF has more reliable race and Hispanic origin data than the DEMO. We assume the CEF is more reliable for two reasons. First, the CEF is current data. Second, our estimates are defined by CEF data categories.

We currently are investigating two methods for sharing reliable information with less reliable data sources:

1. Overwrite DEMO race and Hispanic origin values with the CEF race and Hispanic origin values for people who match (i.e., people present in both the DEMO and the CEF). For DEMO non-matches, use the race and Hispanic origin values as provided by the administrative records.
2. Overwrite DEMO race and Hispanic origin values with the CEF race and Hispanic origin values for people who match. For non-matches on DEMO (i.e., people not in the CEF), use a probability vector to split records into different race and Hispanic origin categories. The probability vector is derived from the misclassification of race and Hispanic origin as observed for the people who match. That is the rate of CEF reclassification on DEMO matches.

5. Results

In Table 1, we have the 8 x 8 confusion matrix between the CEF and PES for race and Hispanic origin. Here, we treat Hispanic as an eighth race.¹⁰ The entries in the confusion matrix represent the percent of people with race and ethnicity disagreement (or agreement) between data sources. The CEF and PES results represent weighted person matches between the CEF and PES.

In Table 1, we can see different patterns of disagreement among the eight race and Hispanic origin groups.

⁹ A DEMO record with a missing race or missing Hispanic origin value has no data source with a non-missing value.

¹⁰ Note, in all our results, we combined race and Hispanic origin into a single variable. This variable has eight categories. Seven categories are for non-Hispanic races and the other category is for Hispanics. Six non-Hispanic categories represent people of a single race. These are White, Black, American Indian Alaskan Native (AIAN), Asian, Native Hawaiian Pacific Islander (NHPI), and a Some Other Race (SOR) category. The last non-Hispanic race category is MultiRace. This category represents people that identify themselves as having multiple races.

White, Black, Asian, and Hispanic values have a strong tendency to be classified the same in both sources. In the census, over 90% of people who reported a race and ethnicity in White, Black, Asian, and Hispanic also reported the same PES race and ethnicity value. Note, our results only reflect the percent of matches, not the percent of population.

AIAN and NHPI have moderate race and Hispanic origin disagreement between the CEF and PES. 67.55% of people who reported AIAN on the census also reported AIAN on the PES. 74.95% of people who reported NHPI on the census also reported NHPI on the PES.

Finally, SOR and MultiRace have a large amount of race and Hispanic origin disagreement between the CEF and PES. SOR has the highest misclassification rate. For example, only 13.89% of people who reported census SOR also reported PES SOR. On the other hand, 35.43% of people who reported census MultiRace also reported PES MultiRace. Moreover, MultiRace has large misclassification with White. For example, 41.73% of people who reported census MultiRace also reported PES White.

On a separate note, there appears to be a fair amount of symmetry between CEF and PES disagreements. However, we will still present some examples of asymmetry between the CEF and PES. The ratio of PES White to CEF White is usually greater than one. The ratio of PES MultiRace to CEF MultiRace is usually less than one. Note, these examples are about comparing two cells, such as PES White and CEF Black vs. CEF White and PES Black.

Table 1: Race and Hispanic origin Confusion Matrix between CEF and PES

PES	CEF							
	White	Black	AIAN	Asian	NHPI	SOR	MultiRace	Hispanic
White	60.37%	0.15%	0.07%	0.09%	0.01%	0.15%	1.86%	0.82%
Black	0.09%	9.83%	0.01%	0.01%	0.00%	0.05%	0.43%	0.11%
AIAN	0.08%	0.01%	0.37%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.13%	0.02%
Asian	0.06%	0.01%	0.01%	5.81%	0.01%	0.03%	0.21%	0.03%
NHPI	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.12%	0.00%	0.06%	0.01%
SOR	0.12%	0.05%	0.00%	0.09%	0.00%	0.06%	0.08%	0.03%
MultiRace	1.52%	0.23%	0.06%	0.18%	0.02%	0.08%	1.58%	0.06%
Hispanic	0.59%	0.08%	0.03%	0.04%	0.00%	0.04%	0.10%	13.92%

It is apparent there is a lot of disagreement between CEF and PES in Table 1. The census has many self-response modes while the PES has only in-person interviews. Response mode may have a differential impact on response value. This non-sampling error would lead to race and ethnicity disagreement between the CEF and PES responses.

Finally, we perform two statistical tests for differences between estimates. We choose a type I error rate equal to 10% ($\alpha = 0.10$). In essence, we want to check if our sample results are statistically significant.

Specifically, we seek a statistical hypothesis test to check whether disagreement is greater than agreement in MultiRace classification or SOR classification between the PES and the CEF. We choose such a test with the null hypothesis: there is no disagreement cell that is greater than the agreement cell. We assume a one-sided, two-sample Z-test produces adequate conditions to test our hypothesis. If we reject our null hypothesis, then we conclude that there is at least one disagreement cell that is greater than the agreement cell. Hence, by our choice of test, disagreement is greater than agreement in MultiRace classification or SOR classification between the PES and the CEF.

First, we test whether there is at least one CEF MultiRace disagreement cell that is greater than the MultiRace agreement cell. We choose a disagreement cell of CEF MultiRace, PES White. The test statistic 3.973 is greater than its critical value of 1.282. We reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is at least one CEF MultiRace disagreement cell that is greater than the MultiRace agreement cell.

Second, we test whether there is at least one CEF SOR disagreement cell that is greater than the SOR agreement cell. We choose a disagreement cell of CEF SOR, PES White. The test statistic 4.695 is greater than its critical value of 1.282. We reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is at least one CEF SOR disagreement cell that is greater than the SOR agreement cell.

In conclusion, disagreement is significantly greater than agreement in MultiRace classification or SOR classification between the PES and the CEF.

In Table 2, we have the 8 x 8 confusion matrix between the CEF and DEMO for race and Hispanic origin. We can see a similar pattern of disagreement compared to the CEF and PES disagreement. There is high agreement between the CEF and DEMO for White, Black, Asian, and Hispanic race and ethnicity groups. There is lower agreement between the CEF and DEMO for AIAN and NHPI race groups. There are high disagreements between the CEF and DEMO for MultiRace and SOR race groups.

One thing that jumps out is the lack of MultiRace people in DEMO. Only 1.73% of DEMO people reported MultiRace, yet 4.10% of census people reported MultiRace. On the other hand, White seems excessive on DEMO. 68.55% of DEMO people reported White, yet only 66.72% of census people reported White.

The results between the CEF and DEMO are detailed below for the interested reader.

White, Black, Asian, and Hispanic have a strong tendency to be classified the same in both sources. In the census, over 90% of people who reported a race and ethnicity in White, Black, Asian, and Hispanic also reported the same DEMO race and ethnicity value.

AIAN and NHPI have moderate race and Hispanic origin disagreement between the CEF and DEMO. 71% of people who reported AIAN on the census also reported AIAN on the DEMO. 69.17% of people who reported NHPI on the census also reported NHPI on the DEMO.

Finally, SOR and MultiRace have large race and Hispanic origin disagreement between the CEF and DEMO. SOR has the highest misclassification rate. For example, only 6.91% of people who reported census SOR also reported DEMO SOR. On the other hand, 25.27% of people who reported census MultiRace also reported DEMO MultiRace. Moreover, MultiRace has large misclassification with White. For example, 51.61% of people who reported census MultiRace also reported DEMO White.

On a separate note, there is an obvious asymmetry in this table. We present some examples. The ratio of Hispanic DEMO, Non-White CEF to Non-White DEMO, Hispanic CEF is always greater than one. The ratio of White DEMO, MultiRace CEF to MultiRace DEMO, White CEF is about eight.

Table 2: Race and Hispanic origin Confusion Matrix between CEF and DEMO¹¹

DEMO	CEF							
	White	Black	AIAN	Asian	NHPI	SOR	MultiRace	Hispanic
White	65.38%	0.04%	0.10%	0.04%	0.01%	0.16%	2.12%	0.70%
Black	0.11%	10.65%	0.02%	0.01%	0.00%	0.06%	0.43%	0.10%
AIAN	0.14%	0.03%	0.43%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.19%	0.02%
Asian	0.03%	0.01%	0.00%	4.49%	0.00%	0.02%	0.12%	0.02%
NHPI	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.09%	0.00%	0.03%	0.00%
SOR	0.10%	0.04%	0.01%	0.03%	0.00%	0.02%	0.06%	0.02%
MultiRace	0.27%	0.18%	0.01%	0.13%	0.02%	0.04%	1.04%	0.05%
Hispanic	0.67%	0.17%	0.03%	0.07%	0.01%	0.04%	0.12%	11.27%

As stated before, Table 1 and Table 2 share a similar disagreement pattern. For example, one persistent misclassification feature is MultiRace. The ratio of CEF MultiRace to PES or DEMO MultiRace is usually greater than one. This means the CEF classifies more people as MultiRace than the PES or the DEMO. However, this misclassification is mainly concentrated between MultiRace and White.

The CEF and DEMO have an asymmetry between MultiRace disagreement. There are many more people who reported DEMO White and CEF MultiRace than people who reported CEF White and DEMO MultiRace. This appears to be a misclassification bias.

On the other hand, the CEF and PES are more symmetrical between MultiRace disagreement. This symmetry implies there is less misclassification bias, though perhaps more misclassification uncertainty. Moreover, the lack of misclassification bias between the CEF and PES implies that the DEMO has a misclassification bias.

6. Discussion

We see that there is a lot of disagreement in race and ethnicity classification between the various Census Bureau data sources.

When we believe that one data source accurately classifies race and Hispanic origin, we can reduce the misclassification of these characteristics in a second, less accurate data source by linking the two data sources and assigning the classification from the more accurate source to the less accurate source. For example, we plan on using the CEF race and Hispanic origin values to adjust DEMO race and Hispanic origin values.

We can adjust the DEMO to the CEF because we believe that the CEF is more accurate. For example, some people may change how they identify themselves throughout time. DEMO assigns race and ethnicity from many potential sources including previous censuses. On the other hand, the CEF is a recent snapshot of the population. In essence, we expect the CEF to have more recent information compared to the DEMO. In addition, the adjustment to the CEF facilitates using data definitions more aligned with the Census.

From Table 2, misclassification is evident. We discuss methods to correct for misclassification and their effects on population estimates when using a dual-system estimator.

¹¹ The percents in this table represent person matches between the CEF and DEMO.

A dual-system estimator uses two data sources to produce population estimates (Zamora, 2022). We use two data frames to improve our coverage of the population. Specifically, the dual-system estimator uses the ratio of the CEF probability of correct enumeration to the DEMO probability of match. We model these probabilities and then use the model to predict these probabilities on the CEF. Finally, we sum these ratios to produce dual-system population estimates.

We will focus this discussion on misclassification's impact to the match probabilities and the final population estimates.

One method to correct misclassification is to match DEMO records to CEF records on PIK. If there is a match, then overwrite DEMO race and Hispanic origin values with CEF race and Hispanic origin values.

For example, assume there is a race group with an excessive amount of misclassification on the DEMO. Let this race be MultiRace. Specifically, MultiRace has fewer than its expected number of records on the DEMO. When we match to the CEF and overwrite race and Hispanic origin, then we increase the number of DEMO records with the MultiRace value. In other words, on the DEMO, we approach the expected number of records for MultiRace. Furthermore, since the reclassified DEMO records are matches, we most likely will increase the probability of match and decrease the population estimate for MultiRace.

However, this method only solves misclassification for records matching between the DEMO and CEF. We cannot match some records between the DEMO and CEF. Hence, we have no direct way to correct for misclassification in these records. To correct misclassification for non-matches here, we assume a relationship between the CEF and the non-matches on the DEMO. Specifically, we assume that DEMO non-matches are misclassified at the same rate as DEMO matches. We split each DEMO non-match into eight shares - one share per race and ethnicity group. We assign each race share the associated probability that we overwrote a DEMO match with that race share. Hence, matches represent themselves with certainty and non-matches represent multiple probable outcomes from classification uncertainty. This method will not provide accurate corrections at the level of the individual person record but can correct misclassification in the aggregate.

For example, assume there is a race group with an excessive amount of misclassification on the DEMO. Let this race be White. Specifically, White has more than its expected number of records on the DEMO. When we correct for misclassification by splitting non-matching DEMO records, then we decrease the number of DEMO records with the White value. In other words, on the DEMO, we approach the expected number of records for White. Furthermore, since the reclassified DEMO records are non-matches, we most likely will increase the probability of match and decrease the population estimate for White.¹²

7. Conclusion

In this monograph, we examined misclassification of race and Hispanic origin. We analyzed the magnitude and patterns of disagreement between data sources used to produce dual-system estimates. We found that people classified as MultiRace represent a prominent feature of misclassification. In addition, we found misclassification bias between the Census Edited File and the Demographic Frame.

In general, we noted that there is much disagreement among data. On the other hand, adjusting data sources to correct for misclassification may reduce errors.

¹² Both these examples also depend on the distribution of matches and non-matches. If there is a preponderance of one or the other, then the majority or minority may have a large influence on the outcome.

We discussed how to mitigate the impact of misclassification on the dual-system estimates. We examined what may happen to estimates when we apply correction adjustments to misclassifications.

We believe that some misclassification may be corrected, especially race and Hispanic origin misclassification on the Demographic Frame. Correction decisions depend on the objective and scope of the project, constraints of the data and software, as well as the input from subject matter experts.

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